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Longline Observer Data System

Data Set (DS) | Pacific Islands Regional Office (PIRO)

GUID: gov.noaa.nmfs.inport:9027 | Updated: November 11, 2025 |

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Short Citation:

Pacific Islands Regional Office, 2026: Longline Observer Data System, <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/inport/item/9027>.

[Full Citation Examples](#)

Item Identification

Title: Longline Observer Data System

Short Name: LODS

Status: In Work

Creation Date: 2003-08

Abstract:

LODS, the Hawaii Longline Observer Data System, is a complete suite of tools designed to collect, process, and manage quality fisheries data and information. Guided by the principles of the NOAA Data Quality Act, LODS is the result of the collaboration and cooperation of scientists, data collectors and information management experts across the NOAA Fisheries Pacific Islands Region.

LODS is an end-to-end data management solution, articulating the four major data management areas of data collection management, data resource development, data maintenance and data dissemination. Every effort was made to eliminate redundant or unnecessary data items and to have the core data collection items be formally adopted by data stewards that would assume the responsibility of maintaining complete documentation and regular review of the quality, objectivity and suitability of the data item.

Purpose: To store observer data and allow end users to acquire data as requested.

Notes:

LODS contains data collected in the Hawaiian Shallow set fishery, Hawaiian deep set fishery, and the American Samoa fishery.

Keywords

Theme Keywords

Thesaurus	Keyword
UNCONTROLLED	
None	Acanthocybium solandri
None	albacore tuna
None	Alepisaurus ferox
None	Alopias pelagicus
None	Alopias spp.
None	Alopias superciliosus
None	Alopias vulpinus
None	Anous spp.
None	Assurger anzac
None	Aves
None	Baird's beaked whale
None	Balaenoptera acutorostrata
None	Balaenoptera borealis
None	Balaenoptera edeni
None	Balaenoptera musculus
None	Balaenoptera physalus
None	Balistidae spp.
None	Berardius bairdii

None	bigeye sand tiger shark
None	bigeye thresher shark
None	bigeye tuna
None	Billfishes
None	black gemfish
None	black legged kittiwake
None	black marlin
None	black-footed albatross
None	black/brown noddy
None	blacktip shark
None	Blainville's beaked whale
None	blue marlin
None	blue shark
None	blue whale
None	blue-gray noddy
None	bluefin tuna
None	bottlenose dolphin
None	brama pomfret
None	Brama spp.
None	brown booby
None	bryde's whale
None	bycatch
None	Canthidermis maculata
None	Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos

None	Carcharhinus falciformis
None	Carcharhinus galapagensis
None	Carcharhinus limbatus
None	Carcharhinus longimanus
None	Carcharhinus plumbeus
None	Carcharodon carcharius
None	Caretta caretta
None	Cetacea
None	Chelonia mydas
None	Chelonidae spp.
None	Chondrichthyes
None	cigarfishes
None	common mola
None	common thresher shark
None	cookie cutter shark
None	Coryphaena equiselis
None	Coryphaena hippurus
None	cottonmouth jack
None	crestfishes
None	crocodile shark
None	Cubiceps spp.
None	Cuvier's beaked whale
None	dagger pomfret
None	deep set

None	deepwater dogfishes
None	Delphinidae
None	Delphinus spp.
None	Dermochelys coriacea
None	dolphinfish
None	Echeneidae spp.
None	Elagatis bipinnulatus
None	Eretmochelys imbricata
None	Eschrichtius robustus
None	escolar
None	Eumegistus illustris
None	false killer whale
None	Feresa attenuata
None	fin whale
None	fishery data
None	Fraser's dolphin
None	Fregata spp.
None	Galapagos shark
None	Galeocerdo cuvier
None	Gempylidae spp.
None	Gempylus serpens
None	giant manta ray
None	Globicephala macrorhynchus
None	Gnathastomata

None	Grampus griseus
None	gray reef shark
None	gray whale
None	great barracuda
None	great white shark
None	green sea turtle
None	green turtle
None	hammerjaw
None	Hawaiian monk seal
None	hawksbill sea turtle
None	hawksbill turtle
None	humpback whale
None	Hydrobatidae spp.
None	Indopacetus pacificus
None	Isistius brasiliensis
None	Istiompax indica
None	Istiophorus platypterus
None	Isurus oxyrinchus
None	Isurus paucus
None	Isurus spp.
None	Kajikia audax
None	Katsuwonus pelamis
None	killer whale
None	king-of-the-salmon

None	Kogia spp.
None	Lagenodelphis hosei
None	Lagenorhynchus obliquidens
None	Lagocephalus spp.
None	Lamna ditropis
None	Lampris guttatus
None	Laridae spp.
None	Larus tridactyla
None	laysan albatross
None	leatherback sea turtle
None	leatherback turtle
None	Lepidochelys olivacea
None	Lepidocybium flavobrunneum
None	Lissodelphis borealis
None	loggerhead sea turtle
None	loggerhead turtle
None	longfin escolar
None	longfin mako shark
None	Longman's beaked whale
None	longnose lancetfish
None	Lophotus spp.
None	louvar
None	lustrous pomfret
None	Luvarus imperialis

None	mackerel
None	Mackerel spp.
None	Magnuson-Stevens Fishery Conservation and Management Act
None	Makaira nigricans
None	Manta birostris
None	marine mammals
None	masked booby
None	Masturus lanceolatus
None	Megachasma pelagios
None	megamouth shark
None	Megaptera novaeangliae
None	melon-headed whale
None	Mesoplodon spp.
None	mesoplodont beaked whale
None	Mesplodon densirostris
None	minke whale
None	mobula
None	Mobula spp.
None	Mola mola
None	Monachus schauinslandi
None	Nesiarchus nasutus
None	northern right whale
None	oarfish
None	observer

None	oceanic whitetip shark
None	Odontaspis noronhai
None	oilfish
None	olive ridley sea turtle
None	olive ridley turtle
None	omosudis lowii
None	opah
None	orca
None	Orcinus orca
None	osteichthys
None	other identified bird
None	other identified fish
None	other identified shark
None	pacific bonito
None	Pacific whitesided dolphin
None	pelagic puffer
None	pelagic stingray
None	pelagic thresher shark
None	Peponocephala electra
None	Phaethon spp.
None	Phocoenidae
None	Phoebastria albatrus
None	Phoebastria immutabilis
None	Phoebastria nigripes

None	Phoebastria spp.
None	Physeter macrocephalus
None	Pinnipedia
None	pompano dolphinfish
None	Prionace glauca
None	Procelsterna spp.
None	Promethichthys prometheus
None	protected species
None	Pseudocarcharias kamoharai
None	Pseudorca crassidens
None	Pterodroma spp.
None	Pteroplatytrygon violacea
None	Puffinus spp.
None	pygmy killer whale
None	rainbow runner
None	Rajiformes
None	Ranzania laevis
None	razorback scabbardfish
None	red-footed booby
None	Regalecus glesne
None	Remora
None	Rhincodon typus
None	risso's dolphin
None	Roudi escolar

None	rough pomfret
None	rough triggerfish
None	rough-toothed dolphin
None	Ruvettus pretiosus
None	sailfish
None	salmon shark
None	sandbar shark
None	Sarda chiliensis
None	scalloped hammerhead shark
None	scalloped ribbonfish
None	Scombrobrax heterolepis
None	sea birds
None	sea turtles
None	seabirds
None	sei whale
None	Seriola lalandi
None	shallow set
None	sharks
None	sharptail mola
None	short-finned pilot whale
None	short-tailed albatross
None	shortbill spearfish
None	shortfin mako shark
None	sickle pomfret

None	silky shark
None	skipjack tuna
None	slender mola
None	smooth hammerhead shark
None	snake mackerel
None	sperm whale
None	Sphyræna barracuda
None	Sphyrna lewini
None	Sphyrna spp.
None	Sphyrna zygaena
None	spinner dolphin
None	spotted dolphin
None	Squalidae spp.
None	Stenella attenuata
None	Stenella coeruleoalba
None	Stenella longirostris
None	Steno bredanensis
None	Stercoraius spp.
None	striped dolphin
None	striped marlin
None	Suckerfish
None	sula dactylatra
None	sula leucogaster
None	Sula spp.

None	Sula sula
None	swordfish
None	tapertail ribbonfish
None	Taractes asper
None	Taractes rubsecens
None	Teractichthys steindachneri
None	Testudines
None	Tetraodontidae spp.
None	Tetrapturus angustirostris
None	thunnus alalunga
None	thunnus albacares
None	thunnus obesus
None	thunnus orientalis
None	tiger shark
None	Trachipterus altivelis
None	Trachipterus fukuzakii
None	Trichiuridae spp.
None	tuna
None	Tursiops truncatus
None	unidentified albatross
None	unidentified beaked whale
None	unidentified billfish
None	unidentified bird
None	unidentified blackfish

None	unidentified booby
None	unidentified cetacean
None	unidentified common dolphin
None	unidentified dolphin
None	unidentified fish
None	unidentified frigatebird
None	unidentified gull
None	unidentified hammerhead shark
None	unidentified hardshell sea turtle
None	unidentified hardshell turtle
None	unidentified jaeger
None	unidentified kogia whale
None	unidentified mako shark
None	unidentified petrel
None	unidentified pinniped
None	unidentified porpoise
None	unidentified puffer
None	unidentified ray
None	unidentified scabbardfish
None	unidentified sea turtle
None	unidentified shark
None	unidentified shearwater
None	unidentified snake mackerel
None	unidentified storm petrel

None	unidentified tern
None	unidentified thresher shark
None	unidentified triggerfish
None	unidentified tropicbird
None	unidentified tuna
None	unidentified turtle
None	unidentified whale
None	unspecified jack
None	Uraspis secunda
None	Uraspis spp.
None	velvet dogfish
None	wahoo
None	whale shark
None	Xiphias gladius
None	yellowfin tuna
None	yellowtail
None	Zameus squamulosus
None	Ziphiidae spp.
None	Ziphius cavirostris
None	Zu cristatus

Temporal Keywords

Thesaurus	Keyword
UNCONTROLLED	
None	August 2003

Spatial Keywords

Thesaurus

Keyword

UNCONTROLLED

None

American Samoa

None

Hawaii

None

North-Central Pacific Ocean

Stratum Keywords

Thesaurus

Keyword

UNCONTROLLED

None

pelagic

Physical Location

Organization: Pacific Islands Regional Office

City: Honolulu

State/Province: HI

Country: USA

Location Description: Hard copy of data is at the regional office and electronic data is at the science center.

Data Set Information

Data Set Scope Code: Data Set

Data Set Type: Database

Maintenance Frequency: Continually

Data Table (digital)

 Presentation Form:

Data Set Credit: Fishery Observers

Support Roles

Data Steward

CC ID: 1454372

Date Effective From: 2025-11-11

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Graham, David Erik

Email Address: david.graham@noaa.gov

Data Steward

CC ID: 837462

Date Effective From: 2018-10

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Harman, Robert

Address: 1845 Wasp Boulevard
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Email Address: bob.harman@noaa.gov

Phone: 808-725-5170

Contact Instructions: Phone or email

Distributor

Date Effective From: 2018-10

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Harman, Robert

Address: 1845 Wasp Boulevard
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Email Address: bob.harman@noaa.gov

Phone: 808-725-5170

Contact Instructions: Phone or email

Metadata Contact

Date Effective From: 2025-11-11

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Graham, David Erik

Email Address: david.graham@noaa.gov

Metadata Contact

Date Effective From: 2003-08

Date Effective To:

Contact Person): Forney, Eric

Address: 1845 Wasp Boulevard
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Email Address: eric.forney@noaa.gov

Phone: 808-725-5103

Fax: 808-725-5217

Contact Instructions: Phone or email

Originator

CC ID: 175815

Date Effective From: 2003-08

Date Effective To:

Contact (Organization): Pacific Islands Regional Office (PIRO)

Address: 1845 Wasp Boulevard, Bldg 176
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Point of Contact

CC ID: 1454373

Date Effective From: 2025-11-11

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Graham, David Erik

Email Address: david.graham@noaa.gov

Point of Contact

Date Effective 2018-10

From:

Date Effective

To:

Contact (Person): Harman, Robert

Address: 1845 Wasp Boulevard
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Email Address: bob.harman@noaa.gov

Phone: 808-725-5170

Contact Instructions: Phone or email

[View Historical Support Roles](#)

Extents

Extent Group 1

Extent Group 1 / Geographic Area 1

CC ID: 43708

Description North-Central Pacific Ocean...including waters inside and outside of our EEZ.

Extent Group 1 / Time Frame 1

CC ID: 43704

Time Frame Type: Continuing

Start: 2003-08

Description: The first trip deployed Feb 27 1994 and trips are still deployed.

Access Information

Security Class: Sensitive

Data Access Policy: Access is restricted to authorized individuals who have submitted a signed non-disclosure agreement. This non-disclosure agreement must be renewed on an annual basis.

Data Access Procedure: Submit a data request to the Observer Program Manager, Operations Coordinator and the Fishery Information Specialist. If needed also submit a signed non-disclosure agreement (blank copy can be provided upon request). Upon approval of the data request by the Observer Program Manager or the Operations Coordinator the Fishery Information Specialist will coordinate with the data requester on fulfilling the data request.

Data Access Constraints: Only individuals with a signed non-disclosure agreement on file may access these data.

Data Use Constraints: Data must not be shared with non-authorized individuals.

URLs

URL 1

CC ID: 43707

URL: <https://ias.pifsc.noaa.gov/lods/lods.html>

URL Type: Other

Description: LODS homepage

Technical Environment

Description: Oracle Database

Data Quality

Accuracy: Data are checked visually prior to data entry by observer and by a debriefer (first check). Data validations are run after data entry and all data are read back to catch and minimize data errors. Second data check is visually conducted on all data with a full read back of all data and data validations are run by second debriefer. Third data check is conducted on selected data fields and data validations are run by a third debriefer.

Completeness Not Applicable

Report:

Quality Control Procedures Employed:

Data are checked visually prior to data entry by observer and by a debriefer (first check). Data validations are run after data entry and all data are read back to catch and minimize data errors. Second data check is visually conducted on all data with a full read back of all data and data validations are run by second debriefer. Third data check is conducted on selected data fields and data validations are run by a third debriefer.

Data Management

Have Resources for Management of these Data Been Identified?: Yes

Approximate Percentage of Budget for these Data Devoted to Data Management: Unknown

Do these Data Comply with the Data Access Directive?: No

Is Access to the Data Limited Based on an Approved Waiver?: Yes

Approximate Delay Between Data Collection and Dissemination: 30 - 300 days

Actual or Planned Long-term Data Archive Location:	Other
If World Data Center or Other, Specify:	Not Applicable
Approximate Delay Between Data Collection and Archiving:	Not Applicable
How Will the Data Be Protected from Accidental or Malicious Modification or Deletion Prior to Receipt by the Archive?:	In a Oracle database which on a backup schedule at PIFSC

Lineage

Lineage Statement: After fishery observers collect fishery-related data on longline vessels they are debriefed post-trip and enter the data in the database.

Related Items

Item Type	Relatio... Type	Title
Proje... (PRJ)	Cross Referen...	<u>American Samoa Longline Observer Program</u>
Proje... (PRJ)	Cross Referen...	<u>Hawaii Longline Observer Program</u>

Catalog Details

Catalog Item ID:	9027
GUID:	gov.noaa.nmfs.inport:9027
Metadata Record Created By:	Eric Forney
Metadata Record Created:	2009-03-23 21:16+0000
Metadata Record Last Modified By:	Matthew Long
Metadata Record Last Modified:	2025-11-11 21:22+0000
Metadata Record Published:	2015-12-10
Owner Org:	PIRO
Metadata Publication Status:	Published Externally
Do Not Publish?:	N
Metadata Last Review Date:	2015-12-10
Metadata Review Frequency:	1 Year
Metadata Next Review Date:	2016-12-10

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Release 6.0.5

Build FINAL (2025-12-02 18:25 UTC)

